

I know how I know: perception, self-awareness, self-knowledge

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Abstract

When a subject has perceptually grounded knowledge, she typically knows how she knows what she knows, and is able to appeal to perceived items and her own experiences in reasoning practices. What explains this ability? In this paper I focus on vision, and I submit that paradigmatic cases of visual perceptual knowledge are such that, when a subject acquires knowledge that *p* by seeing that *p*, she also acquires tacit knowledge that she sees that *p*; I also argue that the truth of this thesis is grounded in phenomenological facts concerning awareness and self-awareness.

1. Introduction

Someone who has perceptual knowledge that *p* is typically able to vindicate her right to assert that *p* by making a claim to self-knowledge. Consider the following situation: I assert that there is a red tomato before me; you ask me how I know or why I believe this; I answer by making a knowledgeable claim along the lines of *I can see the tomato*. In this paper, I focus

on vision, thus by “perception” I mean visual perceptual experience, and by “perceptual knowledge” I mean knowledge gained by visual means.

I take it as a starting *datum* that we are able to formulate knowledgeable judgements of the form *I see that p*, and my aim is to understand what explains this ability: I want to figure out what perception must be like for us to be able to invoke our perceptions in answering questions such as “How do you know that p?”

My main thesis is this:

Main thesis: The acquisition of perceptual knowledge that *p* involves the acquisition of tacit self-knowledge propositionally expressible by saying “I see that *p*”.

The notion of tacit knowledge stands in need of clarification. As with knowledge in general, we need to distinguish sharply between the question of *what* tacit knowledge is from the question of *how* it is acquired, or, as I will also say, what *grounds* someone’s tacit knowledge that *p*. I tentatively give the following answer to the what-question. S tacitly knows that *p* just in case:

- (i) S knows that *p*;
- (ii) S has not explicitly judged that *p*.

This minimal characterisation does not yet give us reasons to think that there actually are cases of tacit knowledge. However, I think that there are two criteria the satisfaction of which warrants attributions of tacit knowledge to individuals:

(C₁) If S tacitly knows that p, S's cognitive and behavioural dispositions are just as if S has an explicit belief that p.¹

(C₂) If S tacitly knows that p at t₁, S is able to explicitly judge that p at t₂ without acquiring any new evidence.

Let us consider some examples. I take it that the following is a plausible case of tacit knowledge: If I know that John is taller than 6 feet, I tacitly know that John is taller than 5 feet. It seems likely that my dispositions are just as if I had judged that the proposition in question is true, and I would indeed be able to so judge, if the proposition were to become relevant, without the need for any additional piece of evidence. Again, presumably, most people have never bothered to judge that the moon is not edible. Yet, I would say, they tacitly know that the moon is not edible: they have the right dispositions, and if asked whether the moon is edible, they would be able to judge that it is not, without any need for collecting new evidence. Applied to perception, the idea is the following: when S acquires perceptual knowledge that p, S also acquires tacit knowledge of seeing that p – S has all the dispositions that she would have if she had explicitly judged *I see that p*, and she could so judge simply by considering the question whether she sees that p.

Describing *how* tacit knowledge is acquired in different cases is a large and interesting task that goes far beyond the scope of this paper. In many cases, it is plausible that one's tacit

¹ For a similar idea, see Crimmins (1992) and Shoemaker (1994).

knowledge of *p* is grounded in a suitably broad repertoire of concepts and beliefs, sometimes paired with basic inferential capacities. For example, people's knowledge of the moon's inedibility is presumably sustained by their knowledge that the moon is made of rocks, that rocks are not edible, and by their possession of the inferential capacities necessary to put these things together.² When we shift to tacit knowledge about our own mental states, the modes of acquisition seem quite different. To perceptually come to know that there is a red tomato, we need the concepts *red* and *tomato*. But it is not clear that having those concepts and the concept *seeing* would be sufficient to have tacit knowledge that we see a red tomato: *seeing* is not semantically or inferentially related to any particular concept that might figure in the content of a seeing.³

That tacit self-knowledge is acquired differently to tacit knowledge of the non-mental world should not be particularly surprising, though: the peculiarities of self-knowledge are reflected in the domain of tacit self-knowledge. In this paper I will focus exclusively on the case of tacit self-knowledge about our own perceptions: acquiring such knowledge, I will argue, is a question of there being a relevant form of self-awareness in perceptual awareness.

The view that I want to articulate results from the integration of two fruitful trends in philosophical research that often remain separate in mainstream epistemology and in the contemporary philosophical literature on the phenomenology of awareness and self-awareness. One is a view about self-knowledge, which I call *constitutivism*, and can be condensed in the idea that there is a kind of self-knowledge such that being in a token mental

² Only minor modifications would be required to explain my tacit knowledge about John's height. Of course, we don't tacitly know all the consequences of what we explicitly know; and when we don't tacitly know certain consequences, we don't have the relevant dispositions.

³ Similar issues arise for tacit knowledge of our own beliefs.

state M of a certain kind⁴ and knowing oneself to be in M are one and the same thing. The other, which has deep roots in the phenomenological tradition, can be summarised in the thought that there is a sense in which an experiencing subject is aware of her own experiences.

The argumentative strategy that I will employ is slightly peculiar, so it is worth spending a word on it. The underlying idea is that the best explanation for the fact that we knowledgeably self-ascribe perceptual experiences in the first-person is that perception involves a form of self-awareness that can amount to self-knowledge; thus, the paper offers an epistemological argument in the form of an inference to the best explanation. However, arguments to the best explanation have intrinsic limits, since one cannot categorically rule out that there is a good alternative explanation. Therefore, I will also provide independent, mostly phenomenological, evidence that the conception of perception and self-awareness proposed here is plausible. Of course, phenomenological arguments have limits too. Thus, neither the epistemological nor the phenomenological considerations can provide conclusive support for my view; however, taken together they suggest that it is plausible, or so I hope to show. Those who hesitate to fully endorse the conception of awareness and self-awareness proposed in the paper, could think of the value of the argument in conditional terms: if the conception presented here is correct, we have a coherent and motivated framework within which to understand perceptual knowledge and its relationship to self-knowledge.

In the next section, I explain in more detail what I mean by “constitutivism”. In sections 3 and 4, I explain the awareness/self-awareness/self-knowledge link.

⁴ Just to which kinds of mental states constitutivism would apply is an open question. In this paper, I am most directly concerned with constitutivism about perception.

2. Constitutivism

Constitutivism says that there is a kind of self-knowledge such that there is a relation of numerical identity between being in a token mental state *M* and knowing oneself to be in *M*.

Constitutivism: being in a mental state *M* and knowing oneself to be in *M* are one and the same thing: the state of *knowingly being in M*.

I take the adverb in the formulation above as a modifier of the state: there is a way of being in *M*, such that one is knowingly in *M*.

There are a few putative proponents of constitutivism in contemporary epistemology. One is Matthew Boyle, who says this about belief:

in the normal and basic case, believing *P* and knowing oneself to believe *P* are not two cognitive states; they are two aspects of *one* cognitive state – the state, as we might put it, of knowingly believing *P*. (Boyle 2011: 228)

In a similar spirit, Rödl writes:

Belief...is a reality that includes its subject's knowledge of it. (Rödl 2007: 101)⁵

Such self-knowledge is quite peculiar, in that its acquisition doesn't require anything on the subject's part besides being in the mental state concerning which she acquires knowledge. Forming a belief might require certain cognitive skills and performances, such as: treating a

⁵ Moran says similar things about action (2001: 31).

proposition as true, considering reasons, having certain concepts, making up one's mind concerning a certain subject matter, and so on. But once whatever it is that is required for believing *p* is in place, knowledge that one believes that *p* comes for free. Applied to perception, the proposal would be that one knows that one sees that *p* simply in virtue of seeing that *p*.⁶ In the case of perception, there is an additional peculiarity: we can use our knowledge of our own perception that *p* to vindicate our right to assert that *p* – whereas of course knowing that you believe that *p* is not as such a source of justification for believing *p*. This is because perception itself is a source of *knowledge*: thus if we know that *p* by perceiving that *p*, then, by knowing our own perception of *p*, we can use the fact that we see that *p* in order to justify our assertion that *p*.

More needs to be said on how this works, but, before that, a preliminary question arises: what reasons are there for being a constitutivist about knowledge of our own perceptual experiences? The question is particularly pressing because, as the reader might have noticed, there is no mention of perception in the passages quoted above from putative constitutivist philosophers. This is because constitutivists often focus on action and states such as belief and intention. They do so for a good reason: their arguments rely on the fact that action, intention, and, according to their conception, belief, are all activities – believing is something that we do, not something that merely happens to us.⁷ But that raises an obvious problem for constitutivism about perception: while one can certainly argue that belief belongs to the active part of the mind insofar as it involves making up one's mind about a certain subject matter, it is not obvious that perceiving constitutively involves anything of that nature, so in that sense perception is passive. Therefore, arguably, the reasons for being a constitutivist about

⁶ I conceive of *seeing that* as an experience and also as a way of knowing. I illustrate this conception in section 4.1

⁷ See especially Boyle (2009) and Moran (2001).

knowledge of one's own perceptual experiences are different from the reasons for being a constitutivist about belief, intention, and action.

In the rest of the paper, I aim to show how to apply constitutivism to perception. Matthew Boyle (2019) has suggested in embryonic form a way of construing self-knowledge about perception that is in the vicinity of constitutivism as I define it here. Boyle notes that the contents of perception are felicitously expressed in demonstrative terms: it is natural to refer to a cat that we see as *This cat*. Of a subject who demonstratively thinks *This cat*, Boyle suggests that the subject's "manner of thinking about this cat presupposes that she perceives it" (22); again, the subject's demonstrative thought is a "mode of consciousness" that is possible in virtue of the subject's "*non-positional* consciousness of her own manner of apprehending [the cat]" (22—23). I think that Boyle is definitely on the right path. However, much more is needed to have a fully developed constitutivist account of perception. In particular, we need to understand more precisely: first, what is involved in being non-positionally conscious of one's own manner of apprehending something, or what is involved in the fact that, as Boyle says in previous work, perceptual information is information that a perceiver is "cognizant of *under a specific mode of presentation*" (2011: 232); second, how this underwrites explicit self-ascriptions. In the course of the paper, I will develop the constitutivist view by arguing that what is required is that the experiencing subject be aware (i) of her own experience and (ii) of being the subject of that experience. Toward the end, I will reconsider Boyle's point about demonstratives in light of my claims about self-awareness.

In the next section, I argue that perceptual awareness involves self-awareness. In section 4, I argue that self-awareness can amount to self-knowledge that one sees that p.

3. From Awareness to Self-Awareness

Before I articulate the argument, I need to make a few preliminary points, both of terminology and of substance.

First, although some of what I shall say plausibly applies to conscious states in general, I am specifically interested in perceptual awareness, which I take to be a specific kind of phenomenal awareness. Perceptual awareness is *phenomenal*, in that there is something it is like for the subject to be in such a state. It is *perceptual*, in that it involves a direct sensory awareness of external objects, properties, events, or facts.

Second, by self-awareness I simply mean that a subject is aware of her own perceptual experiences. For example, if a subject S is visually aware of a red tomato, by saying that S is self-aware I mean that S is aware of seeing a red tomato.

Finally, I use “self-awareness” and “self-consciousness” as synonyms.

My central claim is that awareness constitutively involves a basic form of self-awareness. My main argument invokes a general principle which, I think, is true of conscious states in general, not just perceptions, although the reasons why it is true of perception might not be the same as the reasons why it is true of states such as, say, conscious belief⁸: the *consciousness principle* (CP).

⁸ I will remain neutral on whether the awareness that comes with conscious belief is phenomenal.

CP: For any state s and subject S , if S is in s and s is conscious, S is conscious of s .

There are several possible interpretations of CP, most of which are compatible with my overall argument. However, there is one interpretation which I need to mention just to set it aside: that associated with higher-order theories (HOT) of consciousness, such as those advocated by Lycan (1996) and Rosenthal (1997, 2002). According to HOT, a state s is phenomenally conscious in virtue of a higher-order state that takes s as its object; the second order state will typically be unconscious, otherwise there would have to be a third-order state to make the second-order state conscious, and while this might happen in cases of introspection, there must be a point at which an *unconscious* state of order n makes a state of order $n-1$ conscious, on pain of an infinite regress. While HOT enjoyed significant popularity in the nineties, they have recently been met with growing dissatisfaction. I partake in its detractors' scepticism, so I will simply discard HOT here.⁹

Once we discard higher-order interpretations of CP, we are left with first-order interpretations. On first-order interpretations, being in a conscious state s and being aware of being in s are one and the same condition, not two numerically distinct things.¹⁰ First-order interpretations of CP can be seen as the continuation of a longstanding line of thought that

⁹ The literature on HOT is vast, and convincingly arguing against them would require a separate paper. Here I will only mention two of the criticisms that I find most compelling among those usually levelled against HOT.

1) In order for the higher-order state to make the first-order state phenomenally conscious, it must make the subject of the state aware that *she herself* is in the target conscious state (e.g., Rosenthal 1997: 737). However, for that the higher-order state would have to represent itself as belonging to the same stream of consciousness as that of the first-order state, and it is not clear how an unconscious state could do that (for a detailed exposition of the problem, see Zahavi, 2004, section I; Shoemaker's (1968) classic paper on self-reference is an indirect source for the objection).

2) As it has been observed by many, it is not clear why an unconscious state should become conscious just by being the object of a distinct state (e.g., Bonjour 2003, section 4.2; a more elaborate version of the same argument is given by see Kriegel 2009, ch. 4, sections 3 and 4, and Siewert 2013).

¹⁰ This is a slightly simplified presentation of the landscape, as even within first-order interpretations of CP there is room for disagreement. First, Textor defends a mereological interpretation according to which a mental state x is "conscious iff it is *unified* with an immediately evident cognition ('Erkenntnis') of x " (2006: 411). Second, there is disagreement on whether the awareness that we have of our own experiences is a kind of objectual awareness (e.g., Kriegel, 2009) or rather a *sui generis*, non-objectifying awareness (e.g., Zahavi, 2004).

goes back to Brentano (1874) and Husserl (2001), and has been taken up in different forms in the contemporary debate by philosophers such as Kriegel (2009, 2018), Nida-Rümelin (2017), and Zahavi (2004). The single most important thought that I want to take from that tradition is that there is a form of self-awareness (or self-consciousness) that is not an addition to consciousness, but a constitutive element of it.¹¹

What grounds are there for accepting CP? The most compelling argument that I can think of is the epistemological argument that I promised in the introduction, and which I will develop in section 4.2.2. However, as I have already said, arguments to the best explanation have limits, as one cannot rule out the existence of some alternative explanation. Therefore, in the remainder of this section I shall outline three further points in support of CP, and conclude with a few remarks intended to show that CP only commits us to something that is quite minimal.

The first point is that there are, in the way we speak of conscious states in general, traces of the fact that we seem to find CP pre-theoretically plausible. For example, it would be natural to describe a conscious thought as one that its bearer is aware of entertaining; conversely, saying that I have a conscious thought that I am completely unaware of having seems counterintuitive. This kind of observation is often invoked by those who want to justify CP: for example, Rosenthal traces CP back to Descartes' "commonsense observation" that "the states we call conscious" are "states we are immediately conscious of" (2002: 407).¹²

The second point is that something like CP is often assumed in empirical research on perceptual consciousness, at least partly because it affords a neat framework for thinking

¹¹ E.g., "The awareness of X and the awareness of the awareness of X are one and the same entity" (Kriegel 2018: 83).

¹² See also Gennaro (2004: 1) and Kriegel (2009: 104).

about phenomena such as blindsight and unconscious perception more generally. Merikle et al. (2001), for example, interchangeably describe unconscious perception, or as they also call it, perception without awareness, as a condition whereby one is not perceptually aware *of x* and as one whereby one is not aware *of perceiving x*. By contrast, perception “with awareness, or, in other words, conscious perception” (117), is perceptually registered information about *x* with awareness of perceiving. It is normally thought that although blind-seers perceptually register some information about stimuli, they are not perceptually *conscious* of those stimuli. So it is an assumption of many discussions of blindsight that there is no room between being unaware *of one’s perception* of *x* and being perceptually unaware *of x*.¹³ Of course, it might be possible to explain blindsight using a different theoretical framework. But the fact that CP is part of a widely used framework for understanding empirical results certainly lends it some plausibility.

The third point is phenomenological: when I reflect on what is involved in my having a perceptual experience, it strikes me that I am aware of my current perceptions. I will first explicate the point in general terms and then I will try to make it vivid by means of an example.

To articulate the reflection, it will be useful to zoom in on Nagel’s *dictum* that is often used to gesture to phenomenal consciousness: there is something it is like for a subject to be in a conscious state. I take it that when one has an experience one is in a conscious state in Nagel’s sense. Now, let us see whether Nagel can help us achieve a clearer view. I suspect that at least part of the reason why many find Nagel’s formula compelling is that it captures something that we find in our own experiences: that there is a constitutive link between what

¹³ Thus Overgaard notes that blindsight is “classically defined as residual visual capacity without any perceptual awareness” (2011: 473—474); also Cowey (2010), Weiskrantz (1986) and Marcel (1988: 132).

is often called the phenomenal character of a state (its what-it-is-likeness) and its subjective character (its ‘for-me-ness’).¹⁴ The crux of the matter is of course to figure out what it means to say that a conscious state is *for* a subject. On one possible reading, it simply means that an experience is something that happens to or in a subject: as a matter of metaphysics, an experience requires someone who has it. This seems certainly true, but it does not seem sufficient to capture adequately the phenomenology. An experience does not just happen *to* or *in* someone the same way as processing a protein takes place in one’s body, an experience is for a subject in the sense that it is something that a subject *enjoys*, it is *given* to her. Let me try to crystallise the point in an example. Suppose that I am perceptually aware of a patch of yellow, so there is something it is like for me to be so aware. The phenomenological contention is that, *in* being perceptually aware of a yellow patch, I am aware of what it is like to be perceptually aware of that patch, and hence I am aware of my experience. If I was not aware of what it is like to perceive that yellow patch, there would be nothing it is like *for me* to perceive that patch, so I wouldn’t be enjoying a perceptual experience of that colour in the first place.¹⁵

Some readers will probably remain unconvinced of the truth of CP. A full-fledged defence of CP would require a separate paper, and here I am rather trying to set up an overall framework for thinking about perception and self-knowledge. What can be done here, however, is to show that CP is actually quite a minimal principle, so those who remain unpersuaded by the case I’ve made might be a bit less reluctant to accept the relevant conception of awareness.

First, CP does not mean that we always notice or attend to our own experiences. Sosa notes that just as one “smiles one’s smiles, and dances one’s dances ... so one experiences one’s

¹⁴ For examples of this current terminology, see Levine (1995) and Kriegel (2003).

¹⁵ For examples of this phenomenological point, see Levine (1995: 261) and Kriegel (2003: 106).

experiences”; and given that “experiencing is a form of awareness, one is thus in one sense automatically aware of one’s experiences” (2003: 276). Clearly, one can smile a smile without attending to one’s own smile; likewise, the sense in which awareness is at stake in CP is akin to Sosa’s sense of *being automatically aware of one’s experiences*.

Second, and relatedly, CP does not imply that we are always able to report every aspect of what we consciously see. For example, Block has argued on the basis of experimental findings that sometimes we are phenomenally aware of something although we cannot report it (1995, 2007). But this is not worrying for proponents of CP: it is certainly possible for one to be perceptually aware of, say, three rows of letters, and be aware of what it is like to be so aware, without being able to report all the letters correctly. The general point here is that not all episodes of seeing involve seeing *that things are a certain way*, whereby one attends to a state of affairs, judges that the perceived state of affairs obtains, hence is able to report the content of the propositional seeing. But it does not follow that one is not aware of one’s experience when one enjoys an experience which is not seeing *that* something is the case. Indeed, Block himself acknowledges that it is “platitudinous that when one has a phenomenally conscious experience, one is in some way aware of having it” (2007: 484).

Third, CP is compatible with at least some ways of construing the so-called transparency of perception (Harman 1990, Martin 2002). Discussions of transparency normally start with the observation that when we perceive something, it does not seem to us as though the qualities that we are aware of are intrinsic features of our experience: as Harman says, when a subject sees a tree, “the colors she experiences are all experienced as features of the trees and its surroundings” (1990: 39). Sometimes the transition is made from this initial plausible observation to the claim that we cannot be aware of, let alone attend to, our experience;

however, this seems an unwarranted leap from a plausible phenomenological point to a much stronger epistemological claim.¹⁶ In fact, it seems perfectly compatible with Harman's description that we are aware of, and we can attend to, our experience, by being aware of, and attending to, features of the environment. Thus what seems right to say is, not that we cannot be aware of our experiences, but rather that it is impossible to attend introspectively to the visual experience of seeing a tree other than by visually attending to the tree.¹⁷ Furthermore, certain views of perception *entail* that one is aware of one's experiences. According to naïve realism, perceptual experiences are partly constituted by external objects and properties (e.g., Brewer 2011, Martin 2002). But then, on a naïve realist view, by being perceptually aware of external items, we are thereby aware of our experiences.¹⁸

Let us take stock: if CP is true, when a subject is perceptually aware of something, the subject is aware of being perceptually aware of something. Furthermore, on the interpretation of CP that I advocate, being aware of one's own experience is not a condition distinct from undergoing the experience, it is one and the same reality – being aware of one's own experience is nothing over and above being the subject of the experience.

4. From self-awareness to self-knowledge

So far, I have argued that someone who is perceptually aware of x is aware of perceiving x. Obviously, this is not enough for my purposes, for I have to show how the self-awareness in question can ground explicit, knowledgeable self-ascriptions of the form *I see that p*. In order to do this, I take on three tasks in the next three sub-sections: in 4.1, I explain what is

¹⁶ In her helpful discussion of transparency, Gow (2016) details several cases in the literature in which the two points are conflated, or in which the second point is thought obviously to follow from the first.

¹⁷ Martin can plausibly be read along these lines, e.g.: "I attend to what it is like for me to inspect the lavender bush through perceptually attending to the bush itself" (2002: 380).

¹⁸ This is convincingly shown by Kennedy (2009: 587—588); see also Gow (2016).

involved in *seeing that*; in 4.2, I argue that self-awareness has a specific structure; in 4.3, I consider two possible ways in which the relevant form of self-awareness can ground explicit self-ascriptions.

4.1 *Seeing that*

I have repeatedly invoked a connection between perceptual knowledge and claims to self-knowledge of the form *I see that p*, but I haven't said much concerning the nature of propositional seeing and its relation to knowledge yet. My view of propositional seeing combines two claims.

First, I think that seeing that *p* is a *perceptual experience*. Although not uncontroversial,¹⁹ this idea has been endorsed by prominent philosophers such as McDowell (1994) and Stroud (2011). Of course, saying that propositional seeing is an experience is not to deny that it is a complex achievement. The cases which interest me here are those in which we see that an object *a* is *F* by seeing *a* and its *F*-quality. Seeing that, say, a tomato is red, involves several abilities, such as: discriminating the tomato from its background; experiencing the red colour of the tomato as belonging to the tomato; having the concepts *red* and *tomato*; attending to the tomato and its colour. Furthermore, I take that it involves judging that the tomato is red.²⁰ This takes me to the second point.

The second point is that, in agreement with the vast majority of philosophers, I hold that seeing that *p* entails knowing (hence judging) that *p* (e.g., Cassam, 2007; Millar, 2011;

¹⁹ Some philosophers would say that only the non-committal state of *its looking to one as though p* can actually be an experience (e.g., Bonjour 2003).

²⁰ See Roessler (2009) and Stroud (2011) for a more detailed discussion of the abilities involved in propositional seeing.

Roessler, 2009; Stroud, 2011; Williamson, 2000).²¹ However, I don't mean to suggest that all perceptual experience involves the acquisition of belief: there are varieties of seeing, such as object-seeing and seeing-as, which do not entail any particular belief.

I cannot see obvious problems with the conception of propositional seeing that I recommend, but there is one challenge that needs to be brought into relief. The judgement involved in seeing that *p* needs to be intelligible from the subject's own perspective, it cannot be that the subject somehow finds herself judging that *p* without understanding how she could end up in that cognitive situation, as if she were saddled with the judgement that *p* in the same way in which we sometimes are saddled with a pain. The subject must be, in other words, able to use the fact that she sees that *p* in order to explain how she knows/why she believes that *p*. But in order for her to use that fact, she must be aware of being she herself who sees that *p*: in the constitutivist terms explicated in section 2, that means that the subject's state of seeing that *p* must actually be a state of *knowingly* seeing that *p*. Explaining how the state of knowingly seeing that *p* comes about is the business of the remainder of the paper.

4.2 The subjective awareness principle

If what I have said so far is correct, a subject, in enjoying an experience of seeing that *p*, is aware of that experience. The challenge, now, is to show how this awareness can ground knowledgeable self-ascriptions of the form *I see that p*, which can also be used in vindicating one's epistemic right to assert that *p*. To do this, I will appeal to a second general principle, which says that when a subject enjoys a perceptual experience, she is aware of herself as having the experience. Let us call this the *subjective awareness principle (SAP)*:

²¹ For an excellent discussion of several sources for the idea that *seeing that* entails knowledge, see Ranalli (2014). For philosophers who reject the entailment, see McDowell (1994) and Pritchard (2012).

SAP: for any subject S and perceptual experience PE, if S is the subject of PE, S is aware of being the subject of PE.²²

The main idea behind SAP is that perception does not leave it undetermined which place the subject occupies in the perceptual relation: when you see that there is a tomato on the table, it is not an open question for you whether it is you or rather someone else who has the experience – you don't find yourself wondering "There is a seeing happening, but is it I who am enjoying it?"

In what follows, I discuss in more detail SAP and the *rationale* behind it. In the next subsection, I will discuss phenomenological data in order to illustrate that a subject is implicated in perception in a fairly substantial sense. In section 4.2.2, I will turn to epistemological considerations in the form of an argument to the best explanation: I will take up again the initial datum that we formulate knowledgeable judgements of the form *I see that p*, and I will argue that the best explanation for this fact is that both CP and SAP are true.

4.2.1 SAP and the Phenomenology of Perception

When we perceive an object, the object appears to be at a particular location, such as *here*, *there*, etc.; it also appears to be a particular *this* or *that*. This presumably implies an *egocentric* map of the environment, thus the subject is implicated in the relevant episode of awareness. Of course, saying that the subject is implicated is not enough, for even if the subject perceives an object as *there*, and "there" refers to a location picked out relative to the subject, that does not obviously imply that the subject must be aware of herself as the origin

²² Something like SAP could be plausibly attributed to Kriegel (2009), Nida-Rümelin (2017), Recanati (2007), Zahavi (2004).

relative to which the place is identified. However, the case can be made that the subject is implicated in perception in a fairly robust sense.

Here we have to consider another notable feature of perception: in perception, bits of concrete reality are ostensibly present to us in a way that does not characterise mere thought about reality. In perception, we have a feeling of being in contact with bits of reality that are there in *propria persona*, to use a Husserlian expression (1997, §4). In this sense, perception has a *presentational phenomenology* that other states lack.

It is not easy to state precisely what this sense of presence amounts to, and it might even be that a noncircular characterisation is not available. However, identifying certain structural features will help us get a firmer grasp on the idea. The most general point seems this: perception purports to put us in contact with the *here-and-now*. This, in turn, can be understood as the point that when I see an object I have a sense of being in *the same space* as the object. By this, I do not mean near the object. Rather, that the object and I belong to a single, unified spatiotemporal system that affords indefinitely many further possibilities for perception of the object in question and others. This seems particularly evident in the perceptual identification of concrete particulars: when I visually experience a tomato, I *thereby* seem to know *where* the tomato is: I could demonstratively point to it, and at least in principle approach it and touch it.

Other mental states are different from perception in this respect. I can believe the existentially quantified proposition that there are black swans without any particular black swan being given as present. And even if I believe that a particular black swan is at a particular place, it is not in virtue of the fact that I have a *belief* about the swan that I know its location and I can

identify it relative to my own position in the same spatiotemporal frame. By contrast, if I see the swan in front of me, I know its location because I *perceive* the swan. Thus, the sense of presence that characterises perception is in part a sense of co-presence: a sense that both the object and I are present in the same space, in the sense described above.²³

Furthermore, even states that in some respects resemble perception closely, such as imagination, fall short of providing that sense of being in touch with the here-and-now that characterises perception. When I imagine a tomato, the question whether the imagined tomato and I belong to the same spatiotemporal system is not settled by the fact that I am imagining a tomato. Presumably, an act of stipulation is required to answer the question: I could, for example, decide that I am imagining the very same tomato that I saw yesterday, and that it is where I saw it. I would have thereby brought the imagined tomato under the same spatiotemporal frame to which I belong, but it is not the act of imagining as such that fixes the relation between the imagined scenario and the here-and-now. On balance, it seems that the subject is implicated in perception in a more substantial sense than in other mental states.

Let me summarise: the contact with the here-and-now that characterises perception involves a sense of co-presence, i.e., of the perceived entity and me both being here (in the same space) and now (at this very time). This sense of co-presence, in turn, is in part an awareness of myself as present, here and now. So the argument above links, first, the idea of perceptual contact with the here-and-now to a sense of co-presence of subject and object, and second, this sense of co-presence to an awareness that the subject has of herself in perceiving.

²³ For a similar idea, see O’Conaill (2017).

Further phenomenological support for SAP could be given by invoking the so-called *mineness* of experience, that is, the idea that one is pre-reflectively aware of one's own experiences as one's own. However, although I think this is right, the point is at least as controversial as the arguments that I have marshalled above, and has already been extensively discussed in the literature.²⁴ Therefore, I will simply assume that I have given some *prima facie* plausible considerations in favour of SAP, and I will switch to a different line of argument: both CP and SAP must be true in order for us to self-attribute visual experiences as we do.²⁵

4.2.2 CP and SAP: an Epistemological Argument

Let us recall the *datum* from which we started: when we have perceptual knowledge that *p*, we are typically able to vindicate our entitlement to assert that *p* by making a claim to self-knowledge of the form *I see that p*. Given that *p* and *I see that p* are clearly distinct propositions, an explanation for this ability seems required. I have been arguing that this ability is made possible by the fact that perceptual awareness involves a relevant form of self-awareness. My strategy in this sub-section will be the following: I will start by supposing that CP and SAP are false, and I will try alternative ways of explaining our ability to self-ascribe episodes of seeing. It will turn out that making sense of such self-ascriptions without CP and SAP is difficult; therefore, I will conclude, we have good reasons to accept the principles in question.

Clearly, I will be selective in considering alternative views, so a word of explanation is needed concerning my choice. In particular, I will not consider introspectivist views on the

²⁴ For a recent exposition and defence of the mineness thesis, see Zahavi and Kriegel (2015). For a critique, see Guillot (2017).

²⁵ I want to mention two more considerations that could be adduced in favour of SAP. The first is Searle's (1983) (admittedly much criticized) proposal that the contents of perception are self-referential. The second is the idea that the subject is an *unarticulated constituent* of perceptual experience. This particular point is developed by Recanati (2007, chs. 17 and 19).

model of HOT, partly because these views of self-knowledge inherit the difficulties that HOT have in explaining consciousness, and partly because they have already been incisively criticised by others.²⁶

I will focus instead on Byrne's (2018) inferentialist account and Thomasson's (2006) "cognitive-transformation" account. The main reason for this choice apart from the accounts' intrinsic interest is that there is a general lesson to be drawn from their shortcomings. I will then conclude by going back to Boyle's point about demonstrative reference.

Byrne (2011, 2018) thinks that we knowledgably self-attribute attitudes by inferring that we have them from premises about non-mental facts. Although Byrne's view about belief and intention has been intensively discussed (e.g., Boyle 2011, 2019), the same is not true of his account of self-knowledge about perception. In the case of perception, Byrne thinks, we reason in accord with the following inferential schema, which he calls "SEE":

SEE If [...x...]V and x is an F, believe that you see an F. (2018: 139)

"[...]V" stands for a sentence that expresses a v-proposition involving a particular object x , and a true v-proposition is a v-fact. A v-proposition "concern[s] sensible qualities" (137) such as "shape, orientation, depth, color, shading, texture, movement" (137). So, roughly, the inferential rule means: given a v-proposition involving x , and given that x is F, believe that you see an F.

How does one actually implement the rule? Well, suppose that one "investigates one's

²⁶ E.g., Shoemaker (1994) and Zahavi and Kriegel (2015: 45–48); for further references, see Gertler (2003/2015).

environment, and finds that a certain v-fact, the fact that [...x...]V, obtains.” Now, Byrne says, “vision is, at least in creatures like ourselves, an exclusive conduit for v-facts” (140) and “hence one’s information source must be vision, not audition, olfaction, testimony, or anything else” (140).

I don’t find Byrne’s view convincing. First, it is not true that vision is an “exclusive conduit” for v-facts: v-facts as defined by Byrne include shape, orientation, depth, texture and movement, but we can find out about these facts equally well by the sense of touch (and perhaps, for some, by the sense of hearing) – it is fairly easy, for example, to perceive that a tennis ball is spherical when you hold it in your hand. So there must be additional inferential work done by the subject before she can self-ascribe a seeing. But as soon as we try to fill in the inferential gap, the account becomes extremely implausible. Things would have to go roughly as follows: the subject investigates the environment and finds that there is a patch of *colour* (for which vision really seems an exclusive conduit, at least insofar as perception, rather than, say, testimony, is concerned) at some place; at the same time, she also visually experiences, say, the rectangular shape and the orientation of the object to which these qualities belong. The subject can infer that she sees a patch of red, or some red object, but what should she make of the other qualities of which she is visually aware? Even supposing there to be enough information in the premise for the subject to infer that she is perceiving *one* object, she could only inferentially conclude something along these lines: “I see a red object, and that red object is also rectangular, but it might be that I am *seeing* both its colour and shape, or that I am seeing its colour and experiencing its shape by *touching* the object; the only thing I am sure of seeing is its colour”.²⁷ Clearly, this inconclusive litany is a long way

²⁷ Adding more sensory information will not solve the problem. It is true that if I am touching the object, I will experience its hardness or softness, which I could not experience by sight. But perceiving that the object is hard would not settle the question whether I know its shape by touch or by sight (let alone whether I’m both

off from the confident ease with which we can in fact knowledgeably claim “I see that there is a red and rectangular thing over here”.

Second, it is not clear why sources such as testimony or memory could not be a conduit for visual facts: I certainly can come to know that there is something red and rectangular on the table by being told so. Perhaps what Byrne means is that testimony cannot be a perceptual, and specifically *visual* conduit for a visual fact, but unless in seeing the object we are aware that we are gaining visual access to visual facts, there is no way in which we can build this fact into the conclusion of the inference simply on the basis of the premise that the object is red.²⁸ On the other hand, if we *are* aware that we are seeing the object when we see it, we don’t need the inference. Furthermore, admitting that we are aware of being in visual contact with the object comes down to accepting CP.

My overall assessment of Byrne’s proposal is that it cannot make sense of the transition from the world directed-perception of the fact that p to the self-ascription of an experience of p. In particular, it does not explain how we get from entertaining the content that p to entertaining the content that there is a *seeing* of p. Furthermore, it does not explain first-personal knowledge that *I* see that p.

Thomasson (2006) wants to account for knowledgeable self-ascriptions, or, as she puts it, the fact that “our conscious states are first-person knowable” (1). However, instead of supposing “that conscious states are states we are (in some sense) aware of” (9), she offers what she calls

touching it and seeing it), because I could experience the hardness of the object without touching enough of its surface to make out its shape.

²⁸ Of course, I could reason along the following lines: “I am not receiving any testimony, so I must be *seeing* the object”, but it is extremely implausible to suggest that that is how we make self-attributions. Furthermore, I could be finding out about the sensible qualities of an object by testimony and sight at the same time.

a “cognitive-transformation account of self-knowledge” (1).

Thomasson asks us to consider a case of a “conscious mental state that presents there as (really) being a puddle before me” (10), and it becomes clear later that she means a *visual* experience of a puddle.

When I live through the experience, I am or seem to be aware of there being a puddle. But I could bracket the question whether there really is a puddle and neutrally record how things seem to be in having the experience. Thomasson calls this procedure a *reductive transformation*, because it reduces our commitments, allowing us to record how things are “according” to the experience without taking a stance on whether things actually are that way. So instead of simply living through the experience, I can move to “judgments about how things seem to me” (11), that is, from being visually presented with a puddle, to “making the judgment “it appears as if there is a puddle”” (11). The output of the reductive transformation, that is, the judgement “it appears as if there is a puddle”, can then undergo a *hypostatizing transformation*: we nominalize “appear” and get to “there is a puddle-appearance”. We thus get to a representational content that concerns something different from the initial perceptual content: we started from an experience that only made reference to a puddle, and we ended up with a judgement that concerns an appearance, and all this without positing any inner awareness. According to Thomasson, hypostatizing transformations are “what enable us to speak (or think) explicitly about appearances, experiences, etc., and thus to acquire knowledge about a new range of things—our own experiences and their contents—based on what were originally thoughts, experiences, etc. directed outward towards the world” (11).

I see two serious problems with Thomasson’s view. First, it does not have the resources to

justify the transition from the stage at which we simply live through the experience to that at which we formulate the judgement that it appears as if there is a puddle. Notice that the output of the reductive transformation will be informative only if it specifies the mode in which the puddle appears: the judgement has to be that there *visually* appears to be a puddle. Otherwise, when we subject the judgement to the hypostatizing transformation we will not get an output determinate enough to know whether we are seeing the puddle or rather coming to know about its presence by, for example, stepping into it. However, there does not seem to be enough information contained in the experience as characterised by Thomasson to license the transformation to the judgement that it *visually* appears a puddle. Again, it seems that accepting CP would give us a significant explanatory advantage, as we could appeal to the fact that we are aware of *visually* experiencing a puddle.

Second, I doubt that Thomasson's account can make sense of first-personal knowledge, for the output of the hypostatizing transformation is that there is an appearance of a puddle, not that *I* have an experience of a puddle. Thomasson says that experiences are private, and that therefore "it is only the person undergoing the experience who is in a position to undertake these trivial transformations" (11). This may well be true, but the question is not who can as a matter of fact undertake the transformations, but rather what puts us in a position to self-ascribe the experience in the first person, that is, to ascribe the experience to oneself *as* oneself. The privacy of experience guarantees that if the subject thinks "The subject who enjoys *this* experience...", she refers to herself, but this is not at all sufficient to reconstruct first-personal knowledge. What Thomasson says is perfectly compatible with the subject reasoning like this once she gets to the hypostatizing transformation: "There is an appearance of a puddle; so there must be a subject who enjoys the appearance; I wonder who that might be" – clearly, this does not fit the bill. For the sake of the argument, let us suppose that the

subject continues the reasoning until she stumbles on a first-person formulation by thinking: “Experiences are private, so only the person who has the experience can subject it to these transformations; *I* am subjecting the experience to these transformations; therefore, I have an experience as of a puddle”. Even supposing Thomasson’s account to have enough resources to explain why the subject suddenly hits on the first-person thought *I am subjecting this experience to these transformations*, it is clear that we don’t self-attribute experiences by reasoning along the lines above, if anything because we don’t need to think that experiences are private in order to self-attribute them. Here it appears that accepting SAP would give us a strong explanatory advantage, as the subject would have been aware of herself as having the experience before going through the transformations.

I said earlier that there is a general lesson to be learnt from the shortcomings of Byrne’s and Thomasson’s views. The lesson, I think, is that we cannot satisfactorily account for paradigmatic cases of self-knowledge by attributing to the self-knowing agent simply an awareness of a *non-mental fact* in the first instance, hoping then to fill the gap between the non-mental fact and the self-attribution of an attitude with materials of various sorts such as inferences, pieces of evidence and cognitive transformations. Neither Byrne nor Thomasson can explain how the subject knows that she accesses the fact that *p* through vision rather than some other way; and neither can explain how the subject comes to be aware that she herself is having a visual experience. If I am right, either the subject’s awareness of a non-mental fact includes a form of awareness of a *mental fact* (such as that she herself is visually aware of the relevant non-mental fact), or the subject will not be able to self-ascribe the attitude in the way that has captured the attention of so many philosophers.

To conclude this section, I would like to add further considerations in favour of CP and SAP by amplifying Boyle's initial observation that the contents of perception are felicitously expressed in demonstrative terms (section 2). First, when I see a particular tomato, it is perfectly intelligible from my own point of view to judge that *that* thing is a tomato. Now, we might suppose for the sake of argument that seeing x without awareness of seeing x might prompt me to refer to x in demonstrative terms. However, what is relevant here is not just a form of words, rather the intelligibility of that demonstrative act of reference from my own perspective. When I think that *That* is a tomato, I am aware of *how* I know that that particular thing is a tomato: I am aware that I am in a position to make that judgement about that particular object because I am in perceptual contact with it.

Second, when I see that something is a tomato, I can also direct someone's attention to it, and try to teach her how to recognise tomatoes if she doesn't possess this ability yet. To bring this out more vividly, consider the following sort of exchange. I point to something and say "that's a tomato". You are not in a favourable position to see the tomato, so you ask "which one?" Now, a meaningful way for me to continue the exchange would be to say something like "That one over there, on the kitchen table" perhaps adding some instructions along the lines of "Come over here, you'll see it too". But in order to do this, I have to be aware of my (and your) perceptual relation to the tomato. Thus, the demonstrative character of perception and the role of perceptual demonstrative reference in communication seem to support CP.

The demonstrative character of perception also provides some support for SAP. First, note that there are circumstances in which it would be rational to think "Someone is seeing a tomato, but I am not sure who": for example, if someone shouts from the kitchen that there is a tomato on the table, but I am not sure who that is. Or again: suppose that I don't know what

a tomato looks like, but I am in a room with other people and each of us is looking at a different object. If I also know for sure that one of us is looking at a tomato, and I am not sure whether the object I am looking at is a tomato, I might wonder “There is a seeing of a tomato, but is it I who am seeing the tomato?”

However, things seem different if one thinks “There is a seeing of *that* tomato”. I take it that in order for one to demonstratively refer to an object as *that tomato*, one must have (i) selected a particular object by visually attending to it and (ii) categorised it as a tomato. Therefore, thinking “There is a seeing of *that* tomato, but I am not sure whether I am seeing it” is paradoxical.

If this is right, the demonstrative nature of perceptual content can be taken to suggest both that we are aware of our own experiences and that we are aware of ourselves as the subjects of our own experiences.

While obviously I cannot exclude that some other account could satisfactorily explain the connection between perception and self-knowledge, I take it that I have given a substantial amount of evidence in favour of CP and SAP, especially in the light of the general difficulties exemplified by Byrne’s and Thomasson’s view; thus I hope that these two principles now seem more appealing even to those who don’t think that they express phenomenological platitudes.

In the next and final section, I aim to show more concretely how CP and SAP jointly enable explicit knowledgeable self-ascriptions.

4.3 From tacit self-knowledge to explicit self-attributions

Let us consider a case in which one sees that the tomato in front of one is red, and let us work our way through the subject's self-awareness, tacit self-knowledge, and explicit self-attribution.

First, by CP, an experiencing subject is aware of her own experience. If the perceptual experience in question consists in taking in the fact that a tomato is red, then the subject is aware of being perceptually related to the fact that the tomato is red.

Second, by the nature of propositional seeing, someone who sees that a tomato is red has the concepts *tomato* and *redness*. Furthermore, given the entailment from propositional seeing to knowledge, she knows of the tomato that she sees that it is red.

Finally, by SAP, the subject is aware of herself as the subject of this experience. So she is aware that she herself is visually aware of the fact that the tomato is red.

If this complex structure is exemplified, the awareness that the subject has of her own visual experience that a tomato is red fulfils the conditions on tacit knowledge of seeing the corresponding fact – that is, the conditions on *knowingly seeing that a tomato is red*. In section 1, I characterised tacit-knowledge in these terms: (i) tacit knowledge that p does not involve an explicit act of judgement that p; (ii) if S has tacit knowledge that p, S's cognitive and behavioural dispositions are as if S has an explicit belief that p; (iii) if S has tacit knowledge that p at t_1 , S is in a position to formulate the explicit knowledgeable judgement that p at t_2 without acquiring any new evidence.

Let us take these conditions in turn. What the subject sees and judges when she acquires perceptual knowledge that a particular tomato is red is just that: *that that tomato is red*. There is no reference in what is seen and judged to either the subject herself or the informational channel through which the knowledge is acquired; thus, the first condition is fulfilled. But, although the subject does not explicitly judge that she sees that a particular tomato is red, in acquiring perceptual knowledge that the tomato is red, she is aware of being perceptually presented with that fact. I contend that her awareness satisfies the two other conditions on tacit knowledge.

Many of the relevant cognitive and behavioural dispositions involved in tacitly knowing that one sees a tomato simply coincide with those involved in knowing that there is a tomato: to give an obvious example, in both cases one will answer in the affirmative a question as to whether there is a tomato. Some dispositions will only be present if the subject has knowledge of *seeing* the tomato, though: plausible examples are cases of pointing to the tomato to draw someone's attention to it, or reaching out for the tomato. And, more importantly for present purposes, if asked why she thinks what she does about the tomato, merely having abstract information that a red tomato is present will not be enough to be able to say "I see that there is a tomato over there". But, while there might be differences between the dispositions involved in knowing that there is a tomato and those involved in knowing (either tacitly or explicitly) that one sees that there is a tomato, there do not seem to be differences in terms of dispositions between tacitly knowing that one sees a tomato and having an explicit belief that one sees the tomato: if a subject tacitly knows that she sees a tomato, she will answer in the affirmative a question as to whether there is a tomato; she will reach out for a tomato if there is a reason to; she will point to it if asked where is the tomato; and so on – she will do all the

things that she would do if she judged that she sees a tomato. Thus, the second condition on tacit knowledge is fulfilled.

How does the experience of *knowingly seeing the tomato* occasion an explicit corresponding judgement in appropriate contexts? The short answer is that it has to, because otherwise we couldn't make sense of our successful reason-giving practices. But the way in which this happens need not be overly mysterious. The subject is aware of herself as being perceptually aware of the fact that a particular tomato is red. Now, the only things she has to do to go from this state of awareness to a vindication of her epistemic right to assert that there is a red tomato are: express her awareness of being in the *subject*-position of the perceptual relation by referring to herself as "I"; express her awareness of being in a *perceptual* relation to the tomato by adding "see" after "I"; express her awareness of the fact that a particular tomato is red by adding "that *that* tomato is red", or "that there is a red tomato", or something along those lines. While this complex act of expression involves several abilities, such as linguistic abilities (most notably, the mastery of the first-person pronoun) and a suitable conceptual repertoire (in addition to *tomato* and *red*, one needs the concept *seeing*), it doesn't involve inferential processes, or the acquisition and/or evaluation of any evidence other than the experience itself. Thus, the awareness of the experience also satisfies the third condition on tacit knowledge.

To sum up: someone who acquires perceptual knowledge that *p* is aware of being in the subject-position of the relation of perceptual awareness obtaining between the subject and the fact that *p*; but being so aware amounts to tacit knowledge of being perceptually aware of the fact that *p* (*knowingly seeing that p*), and this paves the way for the subject to invoke the relevant fact (and her experience of it) in reason-giving practices.

5. Conclusion

The topics that I've discussed in this paper are often treated following a twofold division. First, "perceptual knowledge" and "self-knowledge" are often used as labels for different and largely unconnected philosophical problems. Second, phenomenological reflection on self-awareness is strikingly absent from discussions of self-knowledge. But this compartmentalised approach puts us in a bad position to appreciate and explain something that should be quite obvious, namely that perceptual knowledge is immediately intelligible to its possessor, and this intelligibility is manifested in explicit self-ascriptions.

Room for an attractive view opens up when we explicitly consider the connection between perceptual knowledge and self-knowledge, so this should turn our mind toward the constitutivist thought that being in M and knowing oneself to be in M are one and the same thing. The possibility for applying constitutivism to perception opens up when we remove the second division mentioned above, that between self-knowledge and self-awareness. I have argued that perceptual awareness involves a basic, structured form of self-awareness, in that an experiencing subject who is perceptually aware of something is aware of being the subject of the perceptual awareness; furthermore, this self-awareness underwrites explicit self-ascriptions by a subject with the relevant linguistic and conceptual resources. I contend that I have given a coherent and plausible explanation of the intelligibility of perceptual knowledge to its possessor: Seeing that things are a certain way is a self-conscious episode, and the consciousness that one has of that episode naturally bottoms out in a claim to self-knowledge:

*I see that p.*²⁹

²⁹ I am extremely grateful to Donnchadh O'Conaill, who has read and commented on several versions of this paper. Two anonymous referees for *Synthese* have been patient and encouraging, and they helped me a lot to

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